

Steady-state characterization of the PRATIC core at Hot Zero Power with the CMS5 code package and verification against Serpent2

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the steady-state neutronic characterization of the PRATIC soluble-boron-free small modular reactor core under Hot Zero Power (HZP) conditions, performed within the framework of the EU Horizon Europe EASI-SMR project. The present work focuses on the beginning-of-cycle (BOC) configuration of the start-up core, analyzed with the CMS5 deterministic code package (CASMO-5/SIMULATE-5) and verified against high-fidelity Monte Carlo reference solutions obtained with the Serpent2 code. The comparison highlights a very good overall agreement across key parameters, including infinite multiplication factors, control rod worths, power distributions, and kinetic parameters. These results confirm the capability of CMS5 to accurately predict the neutronic behavior of compact SBF cores, even under challenging spectral and leakage conditions. The HZP benchmark provides the necessary basis for subsequent coupled neutronic-thermal-hydraulic analyses under Hot Full Power (HFP) conditions and contributes to establishing a robust multi-fidelity validation framework for European light-water SMR concepts.

Keywords: PRATIC, Benchmark, HZP, CMS5, Serpent2

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) have emerged as one of the most actively investigated technologies in the nuclear field, offering an attractive complement to conventional large reactors [1]. Their scalable modular design, inherent reliance on passive safety systems, and potential for flexible cogeneration position them as a versatile solution within the transition towards low-carbon and resilient energy systems. As a consequence, several national and international R&D initiatives have been launched to explore their technical feasibility, safety characteristics, and societal impact, underscoring the strategic relevance of SMRs in the global energy landscape. Within this context, the EASI-SMR project (*Ensuring Assessment of Safety Innovations for Small Modular Reactors*) was initiated in 2024 under the Horizon Europe Euratom research framework (2024–2028) [2]. Its primary goal is to address safety, design, and licensing challenges specific to European light-water SMR concepts, while fostering a harmonized approach to their assessment and deployment. The project, coordinated by Électricité de France (EDF), brings together 38 institutions from 16 European countries, including industrial partners, research organizations, and regulatory bodies. Through this wide collaboration, EASI-SMR aims to establish a comprehensive framework that supports the safe and publicly acceptable deployment of next-generation SMRs across Europe.

2. CORE PHYSICS STUDIES WITHIN EASI-SMR

Some of the SMR designs under development worldwide are based on soluble boron-free (SBF) strategies that are meant to simplify reactivity control and enhance inherent safety (e.g., CAREM [3]).

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Operating without soluble boron reduces complexity and avoids issues such as corrosion, boron dilution events, and additional waste production. In SBF cores, reactivity control relies mainly on burnable absorbers and control rods, leading to stronger power gradients and non-uniform burnup compared to conventional boron-controlled PWRs. These effects are amplified in SMRs due to their compact size and the presence of heavy reflectors, requiring detailed neutronic and thermal-hydraulic analyses. Within EASI-SMR, a dedicated work package addresses advanced core physics for SBF concepts through two numerical benchmarks: the PRATIC core (Small Academic PWR for Testing, Innovation and Design) developed by CEA [4], and the LDR-50 Lite, a scaled model of the Finnish district-heating SMR by VTT/Steady Energy Oy [5]. Both cores are being characterized under steady-state and transient conditions using multi-fidelity modeling approaches. This paper presents the first step of the PRATIC characterization at beginning of cycle (BOC) and Hot Zero Power (HZP) conditions. The goal is to calibrate deterministic neutronic models under isothermal conditions using the CMS5 code package [6,7], with verification against reference solutions obtained with the Serpent2 Monte Carlo code [8].

2.1. The PRATIC core

The PRATIC core has been conceived as an academic small modular reactor (SMR) benchmark representative of a SBF PWR [4]. Designed for scientific research, yet capable of achieving performance levels comparable to industrial-grade SMR cores in terms of power output and equilibrium cycle length, it is used to support cross-code verification and validation activities within the EASI-SMR project. The core produces a thermal power of 350 MW and contains 57 fuel assemblies (FAs) arranged in a 17x17 PWR-type lattice (Fig. 1). It features different enrichment zones and includes varying fractions of gadolinia-bearing fuel rods to provide reactivity control without the use of soluble boron. Additional reactivity regulation is provided by grey and black control rod banks, complemented by axial and radial reflectors. The design target is a cycle length of approximately 1.9 years, leading to an average discharge burnup of around 34 GWd/t. Overall, the geometric and material characteristics of PRATIC are aligned with those of industrial PWR technology, enabling meaningful cross-comparisons while retaining the specific challenges of a boron-free configuration. Within the EASI-SMR project, the reference specifications of PRATIC have been further refined with respect to the original design version described in [3], to ensure consistency among participating codes [4]. Two core configurations are defined, namely *i)* a start-up core, composed exclusively of fresh FAs, and *ii)* an equilibrium core, consisting of a mix of fresh and once-burned FAs representative of the mid-cycle loading pattern. This work is focused on the start-up core at BOC which is loaded with five different fresh FAs (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Fuel loading pattern, fuel assembly and control rods pattern of the PRATIC start-up core.

3. BENCHMARK MODELING STRATEGIES AND COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS

Within the EASI-SMR project, the PRATIC core will be fully characterized both in steady-state and transient conditions using different tools that combine solutions at different fidelity levels. In particular, industry-like (two-steps) methods based on diffusion implemented in different core solvers (SIMULATE5, APOLLO3, PANTHER, PARCS) and advanced low order solutions (SP3) will be compared against high-fidelity reference solutions based on pin-by-pin Monte Carlo neutronics (Serpent2, TRIPOLI4) and subchannel-by-subchannel thermal-hydraulics (Serpent/SCF). In particular, the current ongoing first phase of the investigations will involve the characterization at BOC. This is going to be performed in a two-step approach, namely *i*) a Hot Zero Power (HZP) exercise with the purpose to calibrate the neutronics models with imposed isothermal conditions and *ii*) several Hot Full Power (HFP) exercises (different core configurations at different power levels) for the coupled multiphysics analyses. In the following, the solution of the PRATIC start-up core benchmark at BOC using the CMS5 model will be presented, together with its verification against the corresponding Serpent2 reference solutions.

3.1. The CMS5 model

The CMS5 code package (Core Management System version 5) is a suite of tools for reactor core design, analysis, and fuel management in light water reactors (LWRs). It integrates modules for neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel cycle optimization, enabling simulation of both steady-state and transient core behavior. Its two main components are CASMO-5 [6] and SIMULATE-5 [7]. CASMO-5 is a 2D lattice physics code that applies the Method of Characteristics (MOC) with a fine energy-group structure to model modern fuel assemblies, including burnable absorbers and complex geometries. It produces multigroup cross sections, isotopic inventories, and related data as functions of burnup, temperature, and moderator conditions. SIMULATE-5 is a 3D core simulator that uses CASMO-5 data for core-wide neutronic and thermal-hydraulic analysis under steady-state and transient conditions, supporting fuel management, reload design, and operational studies.

For the purpose of the PRATIC benchmark, in order to set-up the best modeling options, at first a number of sensitivity analyses have been conducted in order to assess the impact of using different modeling options in the different simulation tools on the accuracy of the results, while maintaining acceptable computational costs. These include for example the energy collapsing schemes at the lattice level (19- vs. 95-groups) and also the multigroup representation of the nodal solutions (2- vs 4- groups). At the FA level, 2D reflective CASMO-5 models were developed for each of the five assemblies loaded in the core (Fig. 2), considering all different combinations of rodged and un-rodged cases. Thermal expansion effects were neglected and lattice calculations were carried out using the P3 approximation for the angular flux in a 19-groups energy structure. The cross sections (XSs) predicted by CASMO-5 were then homogenized and core diffusion calculations have been performed with the SIMULATE-5 code using a 4-groups energy structure. This multi-group representation has been chosen for its ability to better account for the key peculiarities of the small cores under consideration, such as high leakage, strong sensitivity to spectral effects, and tight coupling. At the core level, the SIMULATE-5 code was used with 20 axial nodes (10.028 cm each) and 4 radial nodes per FA. According to the specifications [9], the radial reflector is represented as a homogeneous material, made up of 95 %vol. of SS-304 and 5 %vol. of water. The active zone of the core is surrounded by a row of 'reflector blocks', each block being the size of a fuel assembly. Upper and lower axial reflectors are assumed to be identical, with a thickness of 20 cm and made of 45.14 %vol. of SS-304 and 54.86 %vol. of water. Both radial and axial reflectors are calculated in CASMO-5 with a 1D slab model of fuel and reflector region in series. Void boundary conditions are applied both outside the radial reflector blocks and at the top and bottom ends of the axial reflectors. The 4-group diffusion model was found also to provide a more accurate representation of the axial power profile at the top and bottom nodes, as the additional energy groups allow the solver to capture spectral hardening due to neutron leakage at the core periphery. All CMS5 simulations presented in this work are based on ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data [10].

Figure 2. CASMO-5 models of the PRATIC start-up core FAs.

3.2. The Serpent2 model

For the high-fidelity Monte Carlo reference solutions, the Serpent2 code (v2.1.32) was utilized to carry out both 2D reflective lattice calculations and 3D full-core pin-by-pin simulations (Fig. 3). Geometry and material specifications were taken from PRATIC's reference documentation [9]. Almost default settings were used for both FAs and core models. For the FAs, one-eight symmetry was considered using the *usym* card, while the core was modelled in full, without symmetry considerations. All cross sections were set to a fixed temperature of 600 K (.06c), and no Doppler broadening was needed. The same applies to the thermal scattering law for H in H₂O, which was also evaluated at 600 K. Additionally, unresolved resonance probability table sampling was enabled (set *ures* 1). The criticality simulations (criticality source mode) were run with 10^6 neutron histories per cycle for the fuel assembly models and 2×10^6 for the full-core cases, using 10^3 active and 100 inactive cycles for the former, and 2×10^3 active and 500 inactive cycles for the latter, respectively. As for the CMS5 case, also the Serpent2 solutions are based on ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data [10].

Figure 3. Serpent 2 models of the PRATIC core: FA 3.5% enrichment with 36 gadolinium burnable absorber rods (left) and start-up core in ARO condition (right).

4. RESULTS AT HOT ZERO POWER (HZP)

As far as the PRATIC core, after the finalization of the benchmark specifications [9], the neutron-physical characterization of the start-up core in steady-state conditions at beginning of life (BOL) with the different simulations tools is currently ongoing. According to the description of work presented in the previous paragraph, a hot zero power (HZP) exercise is under investigation from the different partners with the purpose to calibrate the respective models taking into account only the neutronics effect with imposed isothermal conditions, namely considering the XSs at 600 K for all materials and the density related temperatures for all material at 573 K. At the lattice level, a good agreement between

the CMS5- and the Serpent2- solutions for the FA types in the eleven different configurations has been generally found (Table I), the global RMS being equal to 74 pcm.

Table I. k_{∞} of the different PRATIC start-up core fuel assemblies.

FA-type	CR insertion	k_{∞}		$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)
		CASMO5	Serpent2	
C (UOX 2,5%; 8 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	1.16954	1.1705 ± 0.00001	-72
	Black	0.80894	0.8083 ± 0.00001	92
I1 (UOX 3,5%; 36 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	0.93306	0.93362 ± 0.00001	-64
	Grey	0.77296	0.77251 ± 0.00003	75
I2 (UOX 1,6%; no Gd)	No	1.18066	1.18238 ± 0.00001	-123
	Black	0.72688	0.72672 ± 0.00003	30
E1 (UOX 5,0%; 28 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	1.12589	1.12696 ± 0.00002	-84
	Black	0.87078	0.87038 ± 0.00003	53
E2 (UOX 2,8%; 4 Gd pins w/ 2% Gd2O3 + 4 Gd pins w/ 8% Gd2O3)	No	1.21983	1.22112 ± 0.00003	-87
	Grey	0.93624	0.93616 ± 0.00003	9
	Black	0.85276	0.85226 ± 0.00002	68

When comparing the control rod worth simulations (Fig. 4), a slight and systematic overestimation can be observed in the SIMULATE-5 results relative to those from Serpent2. Nevertheless, the overall agreement between the two approaches remains excellent (Table II), with a root-mean-square deviation of 45 pcm. The axial power distribution deviations between SIMULATE-5 and Serpent2 are shown in Fig. 5. It can be noticed that the largest differences occur in the upper and lower axial nodes, near the axial reflectors. In all seven cases analyzed, the RMS values were found to lie within the 0.11–0.40 range.

Figure 4. Control rods (CRs) reactivity worths.

Figure 5. Normalized axial power for the ARI configuration (left) and deviations (%) in the normalized axial power distribution computed with SIMULATE-5 and Serpent2 (right).

As illustrated in Fig. 6, the normalized radial power maps obtained from the two approaches exhibit very good consistency, even in the ARI configuration, where the strongest flux-shape distortions are observed. The fuel temperature and coolant temperature reactivity coefficients have been also analyzed and the differences were found to be in the order of $\sim 2\%$ for the ARI case (Table II). Finally, the effective delayed neutron fraction and the neutron generation time were also evaluated, showing a remarkably good agreement between the two methods (Table II).

Table II. PRATIC start-up core: reactivity coefficients and kinetics parameters.

Coefficient		SIMULATE5	Serpent2	Δ (%)
Fuel temperature (pcm/K)	ARO	-2.39	-2.35	1.78
	ARI	-3.34	-3.26	2.37
Coolant temperature (pcm/K)	ARO	47.75	48.09	-0.71
	ARI	101.93	103.99	-1.99
β_{eff} (pcm)	ARI	703	703	0.00
Λ_{eff} (s)	ARI	2.43E-05	2.43E-05	

Figure 6. Normalized radial power distribution: deviation (%) between SIMULATE-5 and Serpent2.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The steady-state neutronic characterization of the PRATIC soluble-boron-free SMR core at HZP conditions has been performed within the EU Horizon Europe EASI-SMR project. The present study focuses on the beginning-of-cycle (BOC) configuration of the start-up core, analyzed with the deterministic CMS5 code package (CASMO-5/SIMULATE-5) and verified against Monte Carlo reference solutions obtained with Serpent2. A very good agreement between the two approaches has been obtained for all investigated quantities. The root-mean-square deviations were found below 100 pcm for k-infinity and within 0.4 % and 2% for normalized power profiles and reactivity coefficients, respectively, confirming the reliability of the CMS5 multi-group model for compact boron-free cores. The results provide the first validation step for deterministic multi-group modeling of the PRATIC reactor and establish a robust basis for subsequent Hot Full Power (HFP) and transient benchmark exercises within EASI-SMR.

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